

The Attitudes of Nomadic Parents towards Women Education in Zangon-Kataf Local Government Area, Kaduna State. Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was carried out to assess the attitudes of Nomad parents towards women education in Zangon Kataf L.G.A; Kaduna State, Nigeria The study used a survey research design. The population for the study was 100 participants which include primary school teachers, Nomadic parents and pupils from Zangon Kataf. The sample was selected using proportional random sampling techniques. Three research objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire, 100 were distributed out of which only 75 were returned. The method of data analysis was the mean score which were used to find the opinion of respondents to the research questions. Based on the findings, it was concluded that women education does not only end at changing increased enrolment of female children in schools but also includes promoting favourable attitude towards women education, which no doubt, will make the male parents gain happiness and satisfaction in life and the level of parents' awareness and their improved capability to guarantee the freedom of the women to education as is the case with the boy child should be central to parents thinking always. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made: There is need to establish effective guidance counseling programmes right from primary schools so as to encourage the pupils (female gender) education; the Nomads should be made to know that women education in this contemporary society is very vital for sound upbringing of the family and pupil socialization at home; the teachers should encourage women to continue their education and not to drop along the line.

Keywords: Attitudes, Nomadic Parents, Female Gender, Women Education.

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Introduction

The topic has been specifically chosen to highlight the attitudes of Nomadic (Fulani) parents towards women education of Zangon Kataf Local Government Area of Kaduna State. In fact, it is the intention of this study to bring out clearly to the reader why it is necessary to highlight the attitude of Nomadic (Fulani) parents towards women education and the life styles of the Nomads of the area.

It is believed that, this research will play an important role in the development of the education of the Nomadic (Fulani) women not only in Zangon Kataf but also the country at large.

Background of the Study Area

Zangon Kataf Local Government Area of Kaduna State is one of the additional local Governments created on the 27th May, 1988 out of the former Kachia Local Government Area. The former Kachia Local Government is situated between latitude 9° 25 N and 10° 20 N and between longitude 7° 45 E and 8° 40 E it is about 181 kilometers drive south of Kaduna State capital city, Zangon Kataf is bounded on the north by Kauru to the south by Jama'a and to the west by Kachia while it is bounded on the east by Kaura Local Government.

It has an area of 2,668 km² with a projected population size of 816, 370 (based on the 2006 census projection) as contained from the information division, Zangon Kataf.

There are four ethnic groups in Zangon Kataf namely Atyap (kataf), Bajju (kaje) Ikulu and Kamantan (Anghan).

Zangon Kataf is made up of eleven (11) political wards with four chiefdoms namely Atyap, Bajju, Ikulu and Anghan with the total of 52 districts in the Area.

One thing Zangon Kataf boast of is its varieties of food crops, poultry farming and cattle rearing. They are predominantly farmers. They produce crops such as yams, cocoyam, maize, cassava, sugarcane, etc.

Apart from agriculture as the main occupation of the people, they have mineral resources such as uranium, quartz and iron-ore. They are also known of their cultural heritage. One way the various ethnics groups celebrate the uniqueness of their culture is by cultural festivals among which there are Batadon day celebrated by the Bajju of Madakiya, the Atyap day by the Kataf ethnic group. Ikulu day by the Ikulu ethnic group.

There are available infrastructures within the L.G.A. these are educational institutions both public and privately owned. They include Kaduna State Polytechnic (Samaru Campus) St. Louis School of Midwifery, Zonkwa. Science Academy Madakiya and other institutions spread within the area.

Historical Background of the Nomadic (Fulanis)

The Nomadic Fulbe of Zangon Kataf is the same with other Fulbe that were originated from Senegal Basin to be specific Futa-Toro. The Diaspora began their movements as early at 12th century and 13th century, the Fulani's are Fulbe in Futa-Toro were said to have started migrating first south-ward " Futa-Jalon" and then east ward into Mossinas in the Niger valley around 16th Century. The Fulbe were mainly pastoralist. They continue the eastward movement until they reached Hausa Land in 15th Century and subsequently they reached Adamawa and Cameroun Republic in the 19th Century through Borno. (Rather 1978) opined that the Fulbe have introduced inter-marriage between the Negro stock, and the Barbers Tuareg and Moors of North Africa.

Sauta Linjila (1970) stated that Fulbe originated from an Arab speaking, Greek or Roman Egypt.

Palma (1976) discovered that the Fulbe were the result of the union between the Arab and Judio Syrian barbers who came to migrate in 1650 to 1750 A.D

Sultan Bello, accounted for the origin of the Fulbe he said that, Fulbe had Arab ancestry this can be understandable in the light of their Islamic influence and possibly the racial superiority of the Fulbe. Adoloro (1964) described the Fulbe as having cute hair, straight nose, and highly build body. Both male and female are noted of their beauty.

Anomalism is practiced in many parts of the world for various reasons ranging from freedom seeking economy, to education Nomads in Zangon Kataf is mainly categorized

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into two. These are the short and the long term movement, inter-state and beyond national boundaries in long term movement.

The new envy encyclopedia Britannia (1977) defined this type of movement as immigration or permanent change of residence by individual peer group, while Nomadic can be seen as movement which has been brought by economic necessity such as hunting and food gathering or cattle rearing.

Ezeomah (1980) also observed that the short and long term movement could consist of small and large groups. There are times that situation may arise that the aged be settled while the younger ones move with the cattle and occasionally come back to them to acquaint them with progress or check on their well-being.

Another form of movement is seasonal which also differ from Nomadic. This is because movements are not so frequently. It may only take a year that is between winter and summer, this is the types of migrant labour in Zangon Kataf.

Statement of the Problem

The Nomadic parents feel reluctant to send their female-girl child to acquire western education, because many of them feel that western education ends in the kitchen. In the process of this many of their women cannot read nor write because of their negative attitudes toward western type of education.

Culturally, a woman is expected to be cared for by her husband at home. She has nothing to do other than to bear and rear children, look and feed the family. But as society changes, so also is the role of women, but now women are bread winners in some families. The reason being that because of their higher academic qualifications, they are able to secure lucrative jobs which make some of them earn more money than their husbands. Okeke (2000) opined that education will equip women with valuable skills and competences which will enable them to perform their duties creditably. Women education has brought improvement to their families economically, socially, health-wise, academically, and in family planning.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess attitudes of Nomad parents towards women education in Zangon Kataf, specifically to:

1. Determine the attitude of parents towards women education.
2. Find out the impact of traditional attitudes of Nomad parents on women education.
3. Determine the nature of educational provision for the Nomads.

Research Questions

1. What are the attitudes of parents towards women education?
2. What are the impacts of traditional attitudes of Nomad parents on women education?
3. What is the nature of educational provision for the Nomads?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the attitude of Nomadic parents and women education.
2. There is no significant difference between the impact of traditional attitudes of Nomads parents and women education.
3. There is no significant difference in the nature of educational provision for Nomads and women education.

Basic Assumptions

1. It is assumed that Nomadic (Fulani) parents in Zangon Kataf have no interest in Sending their female-girls' child for western education.
2. It is assumed that Nomadic (Fulani) parents think western education is aimed at converting them to Christianity.
3. It is assumed that lack of settlement hindered Fulbe female from western education.
4. It is assumed that Nomadic (Fulani) parents do not allow their daughters to marry and further their education.
5. It is assumed that early marriage prevents female-girl from attending western education.

Significance of Study

The significance of the study is to clear the picture of Nomadic parents' position toward women education in Zangon Kataf. To advice and praise policy makers with guidelines on how to improve the education of women.

Scope and Limitation

The research is restricted to nomadic (Fulani) parents. The reason for limiting this study within this locality is because the researchers were financially handicapped to carry out research from other local Government areas and the time for the research work is not enough in addition there is long distance from one point to the other.

Review of Related Literatures

Women and Education

Nigeria significantly influences the achievement of the MDGs in sub-Saharan Africa because of its sheer size. Nearly one in every four women in sub-Saharan Africa is Nigerian. Hence, the situation of women and girls in Nigeria has a key role to play in determining the progress of the whole region. Nigeria has performed poorly in terms of gender equality. According to the 2012 Gender in Nigeria Report, data suggest that Nigeria ranks 118 out of 134 countries in the Gender Equality Index.

At every educational level women earn less than their male counterparts and in some cases men with less education earn more than better educated female peers. Also, Nigerian girls drop-out of school earlier than their male counterparts. Evidence further shows that more than two thirds of 15-19 year old girls in Northern Nigeria are unable to read a sentence.

Of course, these facts are devastating in their own right, but what is more worrisome is that it seems efforts by the Nigerian government for the past 20 years to tackle the gender disparity in education have not had any significant impact. With regard to women's education, Nigeria's education policy has evolved since the 1980s towards a gender focus

Relationship between women education, family stability and sustained national development

At present, the forces which combine to hamper women education, family stability and sustainable development in Nigeria could be viewed broadly to include denial of equitable access to and participation to functional education, early marriage, confinement to solitary living, subjugation by culture to accept choices forced on women, discrimination and harassment at work, political disenfranchisement from elective and political appointment and exposure to cruel mourning rites upon the death of their husbands, (Oniye, 2010). These cultural barriers and environmental manipulation create inferiority complex in many Nigerian women. Oniye (2010) further ascertained that through the traditional socialization process of our cultural society, women tend to accept negative self-fulfilling prophecy, stereotyping and stigmatization. All these predispositions transmit negatively on the family role and responsibilities, which invariably interplay adversely in the national agenda. Women and development rather than women in development becomes an apparatus for gender issues.

Contrary to the current trend, intensive efforts to foster a gender-inclusive culture from the family level through education, across the board up to higher education, in order to promote sustainable human development need to be vigorously pursued. The legislative arm of government must be precise on the principle of gender equality in education by creating viable channels to the legal rights of women.

Generally speaking, improving access to and the quality of education is the most rewarding investment a country can make. Investing in female education will accelerate Nigeria's economic and social development by enhancing human capital, slowing population growth, and alleviating poverty. According to Agbakwuru (2002) education equips one with marketable skills thereby lifting the possessor up from the poverty arena. Essentially, through education, the individual learns good health habits, principles and practices which promote healthy living and longevity as well as acquire marketable skills that confer economic power on the educated.

Socio-economic Status and Education

Huisman, and Smits, (2010) studied the role of socio-economic and cultural factors, and of characteristics of the educational infrastructure on primary school enrolment, The sample constituted 70,000 children living in 439 districts of 26 states of India. The results

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indicated that most of the variation in educational enrolment (around 70%) is explained by factors at the household level, of which socio-economic factors are most important. And the result also indicated that, in the cities schooling decisions are hardly influenced by supply-side factors. In rural areas, however, these factors do play an important role. If there are fewer schools or teachers, or if the local culture is more patriarchal, rural children (in particular girls) participate substantially less. The major finding of this respect was that in rural areas inequalities between socio-economic status groups are lower if more schools and teachers are available.

It has been found that three major determinants of educational enrolment: socio-economic status, educational infrastructure, and culture have an impact on primary school participation in India (Evangelista de Carvalho Filho, (2008) and Mingat, (2007). Socio-economic indices like the characteristics of households, parental income, wealth, education and occupation, have long been known to be major determinants of educational enrolment and achievement in both developing and developed countries.

Using data from the 1998/99 National Family Health Survey (NFHS-2), a large representative survey covering over 99% of India's population (IIPS, 2000) was carried out. The analyses were performed separately for urban and rural areas. The results indicated that the children of fathers with an upper non-farm job are significantly more in school, both in urban and rural areas. In rural areas, girls are also more in school if their father has a lower non-farm job. Children with a working mother are significantly less in school. Children from wealthier households are significantly more in school (Rose & Tembon, 2000). Breen and Goldthorpe, (1997), in a study, found that household wealth, the educational level and labour market position of the parents is expected to play a major role in deciding the educational level of the child. There is ample evidence that children from better educated parents more often go to school and tend to drop out less (UNESCO, (2010); Huisman and Smits, (2010). Parents who have reached a certain educational level might want their children to achieve at least that level. For educational enrolment of girls, education of the mother might be especially important. Mothers who have succeeded in completing a certain level of education have experienced its value and know that it is within the reach of girls to complete that level. Therefore, we expect them to use the power and insights derived from their higher education to make sure that their daughters are educated too.

In a study, that examined parent involvement among minority families in Catholic high schools, Bauch (1991) socioeconomic status was significantly related to how often African American parents communicated with teachers about school programs and their adolescents' progress. Useem (1992) also found that educational background affected families' involvement in their young adolescents' placement in the mathematics tracking system. According to Useem, "the involvement of highly educated parents in their children's placement at critical decision points in the tracking system is one mechanism by which educational advantage is transmitted from one generation to the next." These findings of the influence of socioeconomic status on parent involvement support the work of other social scientists, who contend that parent involvement in school activities is lower among low-income and minority families than other families due to feelings of alienation (Calabrese, 1990).

It has been emphasized that (Bhalotra & Heady (2003); Basu, Das and Dutta, (2003) that fathers who are in salaried employment are more likely to be aware of the importance of education and hence to invest more in their children's education. The children themselves may also be more aware of the benefits of education. On the other hand, parents are less likely to invest in their children's education when direct occupational transmission or transference of capital is a viable option to obtain a good position in society for their children. Hence farmers and business owners may feel less need to invest in their children's education than people in dependent employment. Also, for small farmers the opportunity costs of sending their children to school may be high, since they are more likely to expect their children to help out tending the land and rearing livestock, especially during peak working times.

Mother's work status may exercise an independent influence over her children's educational chances, especially those of her daughters. According to the resource theory of conjugal power (Smits, Mulder & Hooimeijer, 2003) the degree to which partners can influence important household decisions depends on the extent to which they bring valued resources into the marriage. This implies that mothers who are gainfully employed and contribute to the household income have more influence on family decisions than women who are not employed. More independent women may be able to create better possibilities for their children, and especially their daughters, to go to school. On the other hand, when the mother is forced to work because of poverty, the daughters

may have to take over her household tasks and, therefore, have fewer chances to go to school.

Attitude of Parents and Impact on Education

TNS Social research (September 2003-June 2004) stated that parents' attitudes towards education were generally very positive. The majority (97%) agreed that a good education would help their child to get ahead in life. While 93% thought the qualifications were important to their child's future, 90% also agreed that children learn important life skills at school. Three quarters of parents (76%) agreed that their child's school is good at communicating with them and the majority (86%) agreed that their child's teachers do a great job. Just over a fifth (22%) felt that their child's school tended to be too interested in bright children at the expense of the others, although only 7% thought that the school takes too much interest in their child's home life. Just under a fifth of parents/careers (18%) thought that most of the things their child learns at school are not relevant to real life. A small proportion (14%) of parents saw it as acceptable that if their child did not want to study now, s/he could study when s/he was older. Their study was based on to identify whether there were any differences in parents' attitudes towards attendance between the general population and a group of parents whose children were currently not attending school. This research has not identified any differences in the attitudes of parents in the general population.

Research indicates that most parents show considerable interest in their child's school, and this is equally the case for parents of children who have attendance problems. In an Onsted report (2001) on attendance and behaviour in secondary schools, it has been found that most schools usually enjoyed good working relationships with parents. In fact, most of the parents/careers said they wanted more contact with schools. The majority of parents were appreciative of the concern and time given by head teachers and staff, even when approached about issues concerning their children's attendance or behaviour. However, it was also found that a small proportion of parents/careers were very uncooperative with the schools, and their attitudes, whether confrontational or passive, served to reinforce their children's negative attitude towards school.

In a study of attitude to school attendance in seven Local Education Authorities (LEAs) in England, it was found that most parents/careers believed that children who did not attend school regularly would under- perform in school work, and that it was necessary

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for young people to get qualifications. However, the findings also indicated that parents/careers of children who truant tended to hold different attitudes from parents of children who do not have problems with attendance. Fewer parents/careers of children with school attendance problems believed that pupils who did not attend regularly would do badly in their schoolwork, and similarly, a smaller proportion of these parents/careers believed that young people needed qualifications. This group was also less likely to think that their children's safety was at risk if they were not at school, and were less likely to believe that regular school attendance was important. There were also statistically significant differences between the views of both sets of parents with regard to when children should miss school, with a significantly higher proportion of parents of children with attendance problems agreeing that children should miss school to see the doctor, the dentist, or to help out at home.

Parental Involvement in Education:

Research illustrating the importance of parent involvement for the school success of adolescents spans nearly two decades. Duncan (2009), for example, compared the attendance, achievement, and drop-out rate of two junior high classes. In one class, students' parents had individual meetings with counselors before their children entered junior high school. In the other class, students' parents did not meet with counselors. After three years, students whose parents had met individually with the school counselors had significantly higher attendance, better grade point averages, and lower drop-out rates. Lucas, Henze, and Donato (1990) also found that schools play a central role in determining levels of parent involvement in students' learning. In a study of six high schools in California and Arizona that were providing an environment in which language minority students and others achieve academic success, the authors found that the schools actively encouraged parent involvement. Through newsletters, parent advisory committees, parent nights, and student-parent-teacher conferences, the high schools fostered families' active participation in their teens' education.

Dornbusch and Ritter (1988) studied the effects of parent involvement in high school activities on student outcomes. The study was based on questionnaire data from students, parents, and teachers at six San Francisco Bay Area high schools. The authors found that regardless of educational background, adolescents whose parents attended school functions received higher grades than adolescents whose parents did not. The authors also found that the lowest levels of family involvement in school programs and processes

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were among the parents of average students, minority students, students in step-families, and students in single-parent households. It was concluded that without interventions designed to encourage greater family involvement in these subgroups, educational and economic inequalities will persist for many poor, minority students.

Researchers must also consider race as an actor when studying parental involvement in education. Hill et al. (2004) indicate that the race of the parent(s) impacts parental involvement in education. In particular, African Americans have stronger parental involvement than European Americans (Hill et al., 2004). However, some research has found the opposite to be true. Others, like Hill and Tyson (2009), state that it is unclear whether or not parental involvement varies across race/ethnicity. This proposed study aims to clarify this.

A study conducted by (George, 1995). Search Institute found that four practices of parental involvement discussions about homework, discussions about school and school work, helping with homework, and attending school meetings and events decline significantly between grades six and twelve. The study revealed that by the junior or senior year in high school relatively few adolescents have parents who maintain an active interest in their education.

It has been emphasized that (National Research Council [NRC], 2001; U.S. Department of Education, 2000) the family involvement is the strongest predictor of child outcomes. This dimension associated significantly with children's motivation to learn, kept attention, task 21

Persistence, receptive vocabulary skills, and low conduct problems. Family involvement in education has been identified as a beneficial factor in young children's learning.

Problems facing the Nomads' Participation in Formal and Non-Formal Education

Clearly, achieving the right to education for all is one of the biggest challenges of our times. The Millennium Development Goal“ addresses this challenged through the provision of universal primary education in all countries by 2015. From the foregoing, it is clear that any nation looking for a lasting economic success must raise the literacy level of its citizens. While proportionally small, Nigeria's nomadic people represent a sizable population that needs access to basic educational provisions to acquire literacy skills.

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Education is widely considered as an authentic and necessary tool for national development. Every segment of Nigerian society must therefore have access to education, including Nigeria's relatively small nomadic population.

Nigeria's nomadic people are typically described in terms of what they do not have. They do not have access to adequate food, clean water, health care, clothes, or shelter. They do not possess basic literacy skills. Their children do not have access to basic education. Young female nomads do not have the cultural freedom to marry who they want to marry. Nigeria's nomads, therefore, arguably need a better understanding of their socio-cultural predicament, which many consider as less developed.

Educating Nomadic populations via distance education (and using mobile -learning methods), can be viewed as a positive step towards effective implementation of the provision of Nigeria's National Policy on Education (NPE) on equal access and brighter opportunities for all its citizens regardless of where they live. The establishment of nomadic schools in Nigeria, however, has failed to produce the desired results because of the non-integration of mobile learning technologies. It has been identified that mobile learning consists of any service that supplies a learner with general electronic information and educational content that aids in acquisition of knowledge regardless of location and time (Lehner & Nosekabel, 2002).

In recent years, Nigerian has witnessed a steady growth in mobile telephone infrastructure and a concomitant acquisition and use of mobile telephones amongst Nigerians. Increasing rates of accessibility throughout Nigeria is encouraging more and more people to have access to, or to purchase, mobile phone. Service providers in Nigeria are also on the increase to meet this growing demand, and over time, interconnectivity is projected to be both easier and more affordable, especially for Nigeria's nomadic population.

According to Aderinoye, Ojokheta and Olojede (2007), current education provision aimed at Nigeria's Nomadic People includes „Literacy by Radio“. „Literacy by Radio“ is an educational programme that has been implemented throughout the country. Indeed, radio currently provides instructions and relays messages to Nigeria's nomads, who are typically on the move while grazing their cattle. The provision of tele-centres that provide Nigeria's rural and nomadic peoples with practical skills acquisition are currently being used to teach topics such as health and socio-economic issues that affects their daily lives.

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According to Kinshuk (2003), mobile learning facilitates provision of educational opportunities. In the Nigerian context, Kinshuk's (2003) work can be expanded to include the integration of mobile learning into nomadic educational contexts and programmes.

Mobile learning refers to the use of any mobile or wireless device for learning on the move. Aderioye (2007) noted that it is any service of facility that supplies a learner with general electronic information and educational content that aids their acquisition of knowledge, regardless of location and time. Kinshuk (2003) opined that learning is mobile in terms of space, in different areas of life and with respect to time. This means that mobile learning systems should be capable of delivering educational content to learners anytime and anywhere it is required.

Sharples (2000) observed that mobile learning encouraging flexibility; students do not need to be a specific age, gender, or member of a specific group or geography, to participate in learning opportunities. In other words, time, space and place barriers have been eliminated.

Mobile technologies enables students to become more adaptable to flexible and contextual lifelong learning, a situation defined by Sharples (2000) as the "knowledge and skills" people need to prosper throughout their lifetime. Clearly, these activities are not confined to specified times and places; however, they are very difficult to achieve through traditional education channels. Put simply, mobile technologies fulfill the basic requirements needed to support contextual, life-long learning by virtue of its being highly portable, unobtrusive, and adaptable to the context of leaning and the learners' evolving skills and knowledge (Sharples 2000).

Approaches to Nomadic Education in Nigeria

To improve the literacy rate of Nigeria's nomads, the National Commission for Nomadic Education employed various approaches such as on-site schools, the „shift system“, schools with alternative intake, and Islamiyya (Islamic) schools to provide literacy education to the nomads (Iro, 2006). The nomadic education programme has a multifaceted schooling arrangement designed of 5.3million. in Nigeria, the government set up different agencies to implement education for the nomads; these agencies include the Federal Ministry of Education; School Management Board; National Commission for Nomadic Education; Agency for Mass Literacy, and the Scholarship Board Together, they

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offer a mobile school system wherein the schools and the teachers move with the Fulani Children.

Mobile Schools

8 Mobile schools use collapsible classrooms that can be assembled or disassembled within 30 minutes and carried conveniently by pack animals. While a whole classroom and its furniture can be hauled by only four pack animals, motor caravans are replacing pack animals to move the classrooms. A typical mobile unit consists of three classrooms, each with spaces to serve 15 to 20 children. Some classrooms are equipped with audio-visual teaching aids.

Radio and Television Education

In a study jointly carried out by the Federal Government of Nigeria and UNESCO in 2004, "Improving Community Education and Literacy, Using Radio and Television in Nigeria," it was established that 37.0% of Nigerians owned only a radio set, while 1.3 percent owned only TV sets. 47.8% owned both a radio and TV set, while 13.9% had neither. Findings from the study revealed that radios are easily affordable, accessible, and often more handy to use than TV. Those without TV and radio, however, still have access to the media through socialization in their local communities.

The pastoral Fulani as a captive audience for radio and television programmes have radios, which they carry along during herding. The literate world can, thus, reach itinerant Fulani without disrupting their nomadic life or livelihood. To improve literacy, especially in the rural areas, the Nigeria Government has introduced radio and television educational programmes. The government supplies hardware such as radio, television, and electric generators, and builds viewing rooms for public use.

Although the Nigerian Government has spent a large amount of money to support its nomadic education programme, literacy level among the Fulani remains low, and the quality of education among them is mediocre at best. The current form of nomadic education, therefore, is yet to lift the literacy and living standards of the Fulani people as children of farmers rather than Fulani, constitute up to 80% of the pupils in nomadic schools. In Plateau State, for example, only six of 100 children in the Mozat Ropp Nomadic School are Fulani (Iro, 2006).

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How Mobile learning can be used in Nomadic Education

In a recent Mobile Telecommunication Nigerian (MTN) advertisement, a Fulani pastoralist is depicted making a call and telling other Fulani friends that MTN network was now available, even in the remotest regions. This advertisement portrays the fact the pastoralist-like other Nigerians-can also use mobile telephones wherever and for whatever reason. In terms of using mobile technologies to teach basic literacy skills to Nigeria's nomadic pastoralist, one of the most practice mobile technologies currently available are mobile telephones (Iro, 2006).

Mobile learning systems to a great extent are capable of delivery educational content anytime and anywhere learners need it. In this regard, there are many benefits that Nigeria's nomadic populations can draw upon if mobile learning is integrated into Nigeria's current nomadic education programme. Some project benefits are: Mobile learning will afford Nigeria's nomadic people the opportunity to acquire literacy skills with little disruption to their nomadic lifestyles and livelihoods. The establishment of nomadic schools, in fixed locations, appears to be a misguided educational policy. Indeed, the inherent nature of Nomads as group of wandering people was not taken into consideration during the formulation of this policy. Therefore, one viable option available for these wandering people is to learn through a mobile learning system. One major problems usually faced by Nomads in their wandering activities, is that they lack „interactional“ and „transactional“ skills through the mobile learning system will, to a large extent, equip them with valuable interactional and transactional skills needed to enhance their relationships with the people they meet (Iro, 2006).

Lastly, the modern world is knocking on their door; nomads need to develop a sense of belonging to the larger, modern world wherein learning is a key commodity for survival.

The Challenges of Mobile Learning in Nomadic Programmes in Nigeria

Of course, other, perhaps hidden, challenges still must be faced in the integration of mobile learning into nomadic education programmes in Nigeria. Some apparent challenges are:

1. Nigeria's Nomads may not wish or be willing to embrace mobile learning
2. The sheer cost of procuring enough mobile phones for distribution among Nigeria's Nomads and literacy Facilitators may be seen by some as too costly an endeavor to undertake.

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3. Effective monitoring and evaluation of mobile learning in the Nomadic education programme in Nigeria, as in most developing and underdeveloped countries, remains a big challenge.

Research Design and Methodology

This chapter will describe the research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling procedures, instrument for data collection, procedure for data collection, and procedure for data analysis.

The researcher will use survey Research Design in this study. Primary data will be collected on certain characteristics among the randomly selected sampling from the target populations which are located at various points in the study area. The findings from descriptive survey design will be used to generalize the research results about the target population. According to Osuala (2005) Descriptive Survey Design gives the accurate assessment of the characteristics of the whole populations of people. It is also more realistic than the experimental in that it investigates phenomena in their natural setting.

Population for the Study

The targeted total population of the study was one hundred (100) participants comprising of two teachers each from the fifty two (52) Districts in the LGA.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

Sample size was selected from the target population using purposive sampling technique. This technique was used because the researchers selected districts that are located around the Nomadic parents. The number of primary schools were sampled to Ten (10). The districts include: Magushi Kataf, Jankasa, Magamiya, Zonzon, Zangon Urban, Angwan Rahogo, Gidan Zaki, Gorangan, Manchock, and Gorangida districts. This will give a total of Ten (10) schools as sample for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The researcher will use questionnaire as the instrument for the data collection which will be made up of questions arranged systematically based on research questions to collect data and information from teachers of primary schools. The questionnaire will

be divided into two (2) sections: Section 'A' will be on bio - data and section 'B' on questions related to the research questions.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researchers administered the instruments (questionnaires) to the participants or respondents personally. Before going to the sampled area, permission been taken from the primary Education Board in the LGA through a letter of introduction from the Researchers. The researchers met with the primary school teachers, pupils, Nomadic parents and administered the questionnaires to them. A total of Hundred (100) copies of questionnaires were administered to them within two (2) weeks by the researchers.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The teachers' bio- data and the research questions answered will be analyzed using the frequencies and percentages on demographic variables of the respondents. The percentage will be computed for the calculated 'Agreed' and 'Disagreed' statements (that is, Strongly Agree represent agree statements, while Disagree and Strongly Disagree represented disagreed statements.

The percentage will be calculated from the frequency of respondents to the items. Any percentage agree item with 50% and above will be considered to be significant effect while any item below or less than 50% will be considered not significant. The percentage will be computed for the calculated Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD) statements:

Likert- Type Scaling

Strongly Agree (SA)	–	4 Points
Agree (A)	–	3 Points
Disagree (D)	–	2 Points
Strongly Disagree (SD)	–	1 point

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Research Question 1

What are Attitudes of Nomadic Parents towards Women Education?

Table 1: Mean responses of primary school teachers, pupils and nomadic parents on Attitudes of Nomadic Parents towards Women Education. $N_1=25$; $N_2=25$, $N_3=25$

S/N	Item Statement	Teacher \bar{X}_1	Decision	Pupils \bar{X}_2	Decision	Nomad Parent \bar{X}_3	Decision
1	Nomadic parents believed that western education can converts them to Christianity	3.1	Agree	3.3	Agree	3.0	Agree
2	Nomadic parents perceived that women education is a waste of resources	3.6	Agree	3.1	Agree	3.4	Agree
3	Nomadic parents believed that women roles in the society only ends in child-bearing and cooking	3.5	Agree	3.0	Agree	3.3	Agree
4	Nomadic parents believed that there is risk of immoral behaviour of women in schools	2.6	Agree	2.5	Agree	3.0	Agree
5	Nomadic parents perceived that women needs protection as such cannot be allowed to move freely to school	3.2	Agree	2.9	Agree	2.9	Agree
6	Nomadic parents sees that most of the things learnt in school are not relevant in real life situation	2.6	Agree	3.1	Agree	3.4	Agree
7	It is not in their culture to educate women	2.1	Disagree	2.0	disagree	1.8	Disagree

KEY: \bar{X}_1 =Mean one (Teachers); \bar{X}_2 =Mean two (Pupils); \bar{X}_3 =Mean three (Nomadic parents)

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Table 1 showed that all the items on Attitudes of Nomadic Parents towards Women Education have their mean responses ranging from 2.5-3.6 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50 except item seven (7) with mean response of 2.1, 2.0 and 1.8. This implies that all other items are Attitudes of Nomadic Parents towards Women Education.

Research Question 2: To what extent do the attitudes of nomadic parents' affects women education?

Table 2: Mean responses of primary school teachers, pupils and nomadic parents on Extent that the Attitudes of Nomadic Parents Affects Women Education $N_1=25$; $N_2=25$, $N_3=25$

S/N	Item Statement	Teacher X_1	Decision	Pupils X_2	Decision	Nomadic Parent X_3	Decision
8	Level of women enrolment in Nomadic Primary schools	3.1	Agree	2.8	Agree	3.1	Agree
9	Rates of Drop-Out of women from Nomadic/Primary schools	3.0	Agree	2.9	Agree	3.0	Agree
10	Negative attitude towards women Education	3.1	Agree	3.2	Agree	2.9	Agree
11	Enlightenment on the basic fundamental right of women to education	1.9	Disagree	1.2	Disagree	2.1	Disagree
12	Poor standard of living by the Nomadic families	3.1	Agree	3.5	Agree	3.5	Agree
13	Conservative attitude of the Nomads	3.6	Agree	3.4	Agree	3.6	Agree

Table 2 showed that all the items on extent do the attitudes of nomadic parents affects women education had their mean responses ranging from 2.8-3.6 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50 except item eleven (11) with mean response of 1.9, 1.2 and 2.1. This implies that all other items are extent that the attitudes of nomadic parents affect women education.

Research Question 3

What is the nature of educational provision for the Nomads in the attainment of women education?

Table 3: Mean responses of primary school teachers, pupils and Nomadic parents on nature of educational provision for the Nomads in the attainment of women education
 $N_1=25$; $N_2=25$, $N_3=25$

S/N	Item Statement	Teacher \bar{X}_1	Decision	Pupils \bar{X}_2	Decision	Nomadic Parent \bar{X}_3	Decision
14	Blue print on Nomadic Education provides equal right to education of all Nomads (both male and female)	3.1	Agree	3.1	Agree	3.8	Agree
15	National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) provides primary Education to both men and women in collaboration with States and LGA	3.0	Agree	2.2	Agree	3.1	Agree
16	NCNE provides adult education for the Nomads	2.9	Agree	2.8	Agree	2.8	Agree
17	NCNE provides academic support services to children of Nomads through Nomadic Education Centers	3.8	Agree	2.9	Agree	3.9	Agree
18	Development of Distance Learning Scheme using the electronic media to access the Nomadic men and women	1.3	Disagree	1.2	Disagree	1.7	Disagree

Table 3 showed that all the items on nature of educational provision for the nomads in the attainment of women education had their mean responses ranging from 2.8-3.7 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50 except item four (4) with mean response of 1.3, 1.2 and 1.7. This implies that all other items are nature of educational provision for the nomads in the attainment of women education.

Summary of Major Findings

The findings of this work which was carried out to examine the Attitudes of Nomadic parents towards Women Education in Zangon Kataf were based on the results of descriptive statistics (means). The major findings of this research work were summarized as follow:

The result of this study revealed that Nomadic parents believed that western education can converts them to Christianity, they also perceived that women education is a waste of resources, in addition the parents believed that women roles in the society only ends in child-bearing and cooking, they opined that there is risk of immoral behaviour of women in schools, Nomadic parents perceived that women needs protection as such cannot be allowed to move freely to school among others. This was indicated on Table 4.1.1 from the results of Mean which showed that all the items on Attitudes of Nomadic Parents towards Women Education had their mean responses ranging from 2.5-3.6 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50, except item 7 with mean score of 1.8- 2.1.

The result of this study on Table 4.1.2 revealed that the Level of women enrolment in Nomadic Primary schools, Rates of Drop-Out of women from Nomadic Primary schools, Negative attitude towards women Education, Poor standard of living by the Nomadic families, Conservative attitude of the Nomads are High except Enlightenment on the basic fundamental right of women to education which is low.

The result of this work indicated that the Blue print on Nomadic Education provides equal right to education of all Nomads (both male and female), National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) provides primary Education to both men and women in collaboration with States and LGA, NCNE provides adult education for the Nomads, NCNE provides academic support services to children of Nomads through Nomadic Education Centers are educational provisions for the nomads. This was revealed from

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the result on Table 4.1.3 with mean ranged of (2.8- 3.7) that is above the cut-off point of 2.50 except Development of Distance Learning Scheme using the electronic media to access the Nomadic men and women had mean of 1,2. 1.3 And 1.7 which is below the cut-off point of 2.5.

Discussion of Major Findings

Table 1 identified some attitudes of Nomadic parents towards Women Education. They include: the believe that western education can converts them to Christianity, the perception that women education is a waste of resources, that women roles in the society only ends in child-bearing and cooking, believed that there is risk of immoral behaviour of women in schools, perception that women needs protection as such cannot be allowed to move freely to school among others. This finding concurs with the finding of (Bhalotra & Heady (2003) and Basu, Das and Dutta, (2003) that parents involvement in school activities is lower among low-income and minority families than other families due to feelings of alienation, distrust or a devaluation of their cultural resources. In the same vein, Bhalotra & Heady (2003) emphasized that fathers who are in salaried employment are more likely to be aware of the importance of education and hence to invest more in their children's education

The result in Table 2 showed the extent that the attitudes of Nomadic parents affect women education. These includes: Level of women enrolment in Nomadic Primary schools, Rates of Drop-Out of women from Nomadic Primary schools, Negative attitude towards women Education, Poor standard of living by the Nomadic families, Conservative attitude of the Nomads are High except Enlightenment on the basic fundamental right of women to education which is low. This finding was in agreement with the work of Oniye, (2000) who reported that forces which combine to hamper women education, family stability and sustainable development in Nigeria could be viewed broadly to include denial of equitable access to and participation to functional education, early marriage, confinement to solitary living, subjugation by culture to accept choices forced on women, discrimination and harassment at work, political disenfranchisement from elective and political appointment and exposure to cruel mourning rites upon the death of their husband.

The result on Table 3 showed the nature of educational provision for the Nomads in the attainment of women education. They include: Blue print on Nomadic Education provides equal right to education of all Nomads (both male and female), National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) provides primary Education to both men and women in collaboration with States and LGA, NCNE provides adult education for the Nomads, NCNE provides academic support services to children of Nomads through Nomadic Education Centers are educational provisions for the Nomads. The result agrees with the work of Iro, (2006) who reported that to improve the literacy rate of Nigeria's Nomads, the National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) employed various approaches such as on-site schools, the, shift system", schools with alternative intake, and Islamiyya (Islamic) schools to provide literacy education to the Nomads.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation

Summary

The study was carried out to examine the Attitudes of Nomadic parents towards Women Education in Zangon Kataf. We were able to discover that: Nomadic parents believed that western education can converts them to Christianity, Nomadic parents perceived that women education is a waste of resources, Nomadic parents believed that women roles in the society only ends in child-bearing and cooking, Nomadic parents believed that there is risk of immoral behaviour of women in schools, Nomadic parents perceived that women needs protection as such cannot be allowed to move freely to school are the attitudes of nomadic parents towards women education; the Level of women enrolment in Nomadic Primary schools, Rates of Drop-Out of women from Nomadic Primary schools, Negative attitude towards women Education, Poor standard of living by the Nomadic families, Conservative attitude of the Nomads are the extent to which the attitudes of nomadic parents affects women education; the Blue print on Nomadic Education provides equal right to education of all Nomads (both male and female), National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) provides primary Education to both men and women in collaboration with States and LGA, NCNE provides adult education for the Nomads, NCNE provides academic support services to children of Nomads through Nomadic Education Centers are educational provisions for the nomads.

Conclusion

The women education does not only end at changing increased enrolment of female children in schools but also includes promoting favourable attitude towards women education, which no doubt, will make the male parents gain happiness and satisfaction in life. The level of parents' awareness and their improved capability to guarantee the freedom of the women to education as is the case with the boy child should be central to parents thinking always.

Recommendations

1. There is need to establish effective guidance counseling programmes in schools right from primary school so as to encourage the female gender education.
2. Kaduna State Ministry of Education should establish a community based "Education Counseling Committees" to carry out counseling in rural areas for parents with negative attitude towards women education to favourably change their attitudes positively towards the women education.
3. National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) should establish a female education unit to attain the equity issue in the Universal Basic Education.

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